

A note on some direct and indirect effects of Udbatta disease on some rice yield components

N. Shivanandappa, junior pathologist, Regional Research Station, University of Agricultural Sciences, Mission Compound, Shimoga, Karnataka, India

A study at Mandya, India, in kharif 1974 showed a reduction in the number of healthy panicles, panicle length, number of primary rachis per panicle and grain weight per hill of rice culture MR 81 that had been affected by *Ephelis oryzae* Syd. – Udbatta disease (see table).

Shivanandappa et al. earlier reported yield loss in Udbatta-affected MR 118 paddy culture to be 2.44 panicles/hill with an intensity of 2.59. In another study, Shivanandappa and Govindu found that in MR 81 the direct and indirect losses due to Udbatta disease were 2.04 and 0.36 panicles/hill. The slight differences in direct and indirect losses in the present study may be due not only to varietal differences but also to the higher intensity of the disease. The data confirm that Udbatta disease affects the rice plant both directly and indirectly.

Effect of Udbatta disease on some yield components and yield of paddy culture MR 81. Rice Research Station, Mandya, 1974.

	Panicles (no.)			Panicle length (cm)	Primary rachis per panicle (no.)	Grain weight (g/hill)
	Healthy	Diseased	Total			
Healthy hills	10.82	–	10.82	16.15	7.18	15.30
Diseased hills	9.24	1.30	10.54	15.65	6.83	12.45
Loss	1.58	1.30	0.28	0.50	0.35	2.85

Simultaneous occurrence of node blast and stem rot on Basmati 370

B. K. Rattan and C. D. Mayee, Regional Rice Research Station, Punjab Agricultural University, Kapurthala, India

At the Regional Rice Research Station, Kapurthala, Punjab, rice variety Basmati 370 was simultaneously infected by two diseases, node blast caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav., and stem rot caused by *Magnaporthe salvinii* (Catt.) Krause and Webster. To examine the possible relationship between the two diseases, we studied five blocks of Basmati 370 which were uniformly affected by node blast and stem rot.

Results indicated a definite association between node blast and stem rot. Although blast incidence was low and stem rot was high, they decreased panicle weight both individually and in combination.

Averaged over different categories, node blast and stem rot registered 17.09 and 35.87 percent infection, respectively. A high positive correlation ($r = 0.926$) between occurrences of the two diseases indicated that the increase in one was accompanied by corresponding increase in the other, and the reduction in panicle weight on account of either disease was stimulated by the other.

Although the incidence of stem rot was higher than that of node blast, the reduction in panicle weight due to node blast was appreciably greater than that due to stem rot.

Both diseases usually appear late in rice growth. The stem rot pathogen is an established wound parasite. Wounds may be caused by such factors as insect attack or lodging. Node blast causes lodging; thus it is logical to expect more severe stem rot in plants that are infected by node blast. Earlier, researchers had

reported varieties of the Basmati group to be resistant to stem rot in Punjab. The decline of relative resistance may be due partly to the predisposition to stem rot development of Basmati 370 infected by node blast.

Seminar on planthoppers and leafhoppers of the rice crop, Yogyakarta, Indonesia, June 1–3, 1976

O. Mochida, IRRI-Central Research Institute for Agriculture (CRIA), and S. Tatang, CRIA, Sukamandi, Indonesia

A seminar on rice planthoppers and leafhoppers was held at the first meeting of the Entomological Society of Indonesia (President, Ir. Soenardi). It was sponsored by the Faculty of Agriculture of Gadjah Mada University and the Entomological Society. About 200 participants, including plant protection specialists, entomologists, agronomists, breeders, and agricultural spray pilots attended. Thirty-six papers were presented. The participation of many persons in various fields indicated the importance of the brown planthopper in Indonesia. About 290,324 tons of rice were lost to the brown planthopper and to grassy stunt virus in the fiscal year 1974–75.

Influence of nitrogen fertilization on the development of bacterial blight

S. Kannaiyan, A. Venkata Rao, T. L. Subramanian, K. Chandramani, and K. Tera, Regional Agricultural Research Station, Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, India

EDITOR'S NOTE: In the article carrying the above title, which appeared in IRRN 1:1 (October 1976), the name of the senior author, S. Kannaiyan, was inadvertently omitted.